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Version 1.0 Date of posting: 19/06/2026

Title:

The Wrongs of Backsliding on Climate: Collective Political Akrasia and Climate Inaction

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Abstract

Failures of governments to act on anthropogenic climate change cannot be grasped in terms of denial alone. One way of expanding the vocabulary for describing, criticising and holding to account government inaction is through the concept of collective akrasia. Akrasia denotes voluntary action by agents against their best judgements about the right course of action. This paper argues this can apply to governments as well as individuals. The paper outlines an approach to collective political akrasia that builds on Amélie Oksenberg Rorty's work on the social and political sources of akrasia and Philip Pettit's proposal for collective akrasia. It argues this concept contributes something valuable to the political and ethical vocabulary available for holding governments to account: Criticizing someone for their akratic character is different from criticizing them as ignorant, vicious or powerless, and the same goes for governments. Considering the place of akrasia in politics also opens broader reflection on questions of government agency and accountability – even if it turns out that akrasia is the wrong diagnosis, it is useful to consider why.

Keywords: Collective Akrasia; Climate Inaction; Environmental Politics; Climate Crisis

Declarations:

This work was supported by the European Regional Development Fund project ‘Beyond Security: Role of Conflict in Resilience-Building’ (registration number:

CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004595), which was implemented by the project partner, the Institute of Philosophy, Czech Academy of Sciences (IP CAS).

The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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Introduction

It is (or should be) uncontroversial to say that there is a vast gap between the urgency posed by anthropogenic climate change and the action taken to address it. While this lack of action applies across areas of society, it is perhaps most acute when it comes to the action of states and governments. For many governments, however, this inaction sits alongside a variety of public statements recognizing the reality of climate change and commitments to mitigate it. While explicit climate denial remains a powerful force, not least in the politics of the United States, it does not seem to capture what is at stake in all such failures. In response, various attempts have been made to expand the vocabulary for discussing climate inaction, for example through more sophisticated treatments of denial (Malm and the Zetkin Collective 2021), strategic ignorance (McGoey 2019), or closer attention to rhetorical structure of climate discourse (Guenther 2024).

This paper proposes one possible expansion of this vocabulary in the form of collective political akrasia. We suggest that *some* of these failures can be best grasped as examples of *akrasia* on the part of governments. In its classical sense, akrasia describes voluntary action by agents against their best judgements about the right course of action. It is thus a form of voluntary wrongdoing, in at least the minimal sense that the agent believes that what they are doing is wrong. This concept is not unfamiliar in discussions of ecological action – for example in people’s failure to recycle or continuing to eat meat despite their ethical commitments – but we suggest that it might also be applied to governments as

collective agents, and that doing so expands the vocabulary available for analyzing, criticizing and rectifying the problem of government inaction on climate change.

Why invoke akrasia? First, akrasia is a concept (since Aristotle) designed to appropriately distinguish between different kinds of wrongdoing in order to identify which possibilities exist for reform and responsibility. In the same spirit, we think that the concept contributes something valuable to the political and ethical vocabulary available for holding governments to account: Holding a government accountable for ‘backsliding’ or failing to live up to its stated values is different to holding it accountable for having the wrong values. Criticizing a government that professes to ‘believe the science’ is different to criticizing one that denies it. The second reason flows from this: Just as an analysis in terms of akrasia helps identify responsibility, it can help identify the sources of the akratic failure to act, and thus identify how and where that failure might be overcome. This information is relevant to both the subject themselves, so long as they are sufficiently committed to reform, and for those who would wish to reform them.

To develop our argument, we first (in section 1) draw on an account of individual akrasia grounded in the work of Amelie Oksenberg Rorty, which emphasizes the social and political sources of akrasia and provides valuable resources for extending akrasia to the collective level. We then (in section 2) develop this extension in critical dialogue with Philip Pettit’s account of collective akrasia, before (in section 3) suggesting how it might be applied to the specific case of climate inaction. Finally, we respond (in section 4) to some possible objections to our proposal, and in doing so draw out what we take to be its distinctive contribution.

1. Individual akrasia and the archaeology of the self

A professed anti-racist crosses the road when approaching a group of black teenagers, and reflects she would have behaved differently were they white (Comay Del Junco 2018, p. 77). A philosopher is completely convinced by the moral force of arguments for vegetarianism; but eats meat (Aaltola 2019). A stockbroker who volunteers to help her elderly church congregation at the same time manipulates them into buying junk bonds despite knowing it is wrong and feeling guilty for it (Rorty 1997). These examples, while diverse, all appear to involve the phenomenon called akrasia: the individual freely and voluntarily acts against their overall beliefs about the right thing to do (what we will call, following Rorty, their ‘preferred alternative’) in favour of something else (the ‘akratic alternative’), with (in some sense) knowledge that they are doing so.

Akrasia is one of the oldest concepts in Western philosophy. In the *Protagoras*, Plato’s Socrates (1992, p. 49) is generally interpreted as rejecting it as a genuine possibility,

denying the popular view that (moral) knowledge can be ‘dragged around by [pleasure, pain, love or fear], as if it were a slave.’ Aristotle (1999, pp. 100-101), in the *Nicomachean Ethics*, adopts a different approach: if the majority can speak of the possibility of pleasure dragging knowledge around, there is some phenomenon worthy of explanation and exploration.

Precisely *how* Aristotle explains it is subject to much dispute and interpretation, hinging in part on whether he is read as ultimately accepting the possibility that knowledge can be ‘dragged around’ by pleasure, or whether what is at stake is some kind of defective or inadequate form of knowledge (Cagnoli Fiecconi 2018). However, *why* he seeks to explain it seems clearer: As part of the general project of the *Nicomachean Ethics*, he is identifying different forms of virtuous and vicious character to consider how they might be reformed (Burnyeat 1980; Rorty 1980). The akratic is a particular type of character, distinct from ‘bestial’ person, who brutishly reacts to certain stimuli, the vicious person, who is in complete ignorance of the good, and the self-indulgent person, who lacks an understanding of proper ends of action, pursuing pleasure for its own sake, rather than appropriately taking pleasure in actions that are good for their own sake (Aristotle 1999, pp. 104-110). Distinct from these, the *akrates* possesses the correct ends, can recognize them as such, but fails to act on this knowledge. Aristotle’s treatment thus sets the conditions for akratic action: the *akrates* must act voluntarily (since compelled action is not akratic), they must be in some appropriate sense aware of what they do and how it violates their better judgement, and they must be a genuine subject, capable of seeing themselves and their life as a coherent whole.

Debates around akrasia resurface in the context of twentieth century analytical philosophy, discussed largely under the rubric of ‘weakness of will’ (see Stroud and Svirsky 2021). In this debate, akrasia is less of interest as a specifically *moral* problem, but instead because of the challenge it poses to the idea that evaluative judgements play a distinctive role in guiding action. Because of this, R.M. Hare (1952) casts himself in the role of Socrates in the modern debate, insisting that any apparently akratic action must in fact either reveal some insincerity in stated moral beliefs or some compulsion or inability to act. In contrast, Donald Davidson’s influential account attempted to defend the *possibility* of akrasia without abandoning a role for evaluative judgements in explaining action. Davidson does this by distinguishing ‘all-things-considered’ judgements from ‘all-out’ judgements. Akrasia involves an agent acting against their ‘all-things-considered’ judgement about the best course of action, which, although more comprehensive than an initial *prima facie* judgement, remains conditional, dependent on a balance of considerations (see Stroud and Svirsky 2021). There remains a logical gap between this and the ‘all out’ judgement that the action is the right thing to do.

Because of this logical gap, the agent who does not act on their ‘all things considered’ judgement is not involved in a practical contradiction – they do not commit ‘a simple logical blunder’ (Hare 1952, p. 40). Rather, they fall short of drawing an ‘all out’ judgement, remaining only at the stage of weighing reasons. They, moreover, possess some reasons to act counter to that judgement, and act on the lesser reason, rather than the greater. Davidson, however, insists that the action is, despite this, *irrational*, since the agent has no good reason to do something other than what they judge best. The failure to move from an ‘all things considered’ to an ‘all out’ judgement violates what he calls ‘the principle of continence’, which tells us ‘perform the action judged best on the basis of all available relevant reasons’ (p. 41).

Davidson’s account captures an important element of akratic action, namely that even if it is *irrational*, it is not *without reason* (see Mele 1987, p. 75). However, his approach seems to rule out apparently intelligible cases in which the *akrates* insists that they possess not merely an all-things-considered judgement, but an all-out one (see Stroud and Strinsky, 2021, Section 3.1). Consider the cases with which we began this section: any one of these individuals might plausibly insist their beliefs about the wrongness of racism, vegetarianism and cheating the elderly are unconditional and decisive, not merely all-things-considered.

A quite different trend in twentieth century discussions of akrasia is represented by Amelie Oksenberg Rorty, who developed a complex account of akrasia over a series of articles in the 1980s and 1990s. Rorty similarly wants to recognize akrasia as a real possibility, but suggests that doing so requires approaching it not as a marginal puzzle, but as something that reveals important features of human agency (see Rorty 1987, pp. 115-116). Rorty’s work is valuable for our purposes for two reasons: First, it self-consciously places akrasia within social and political contexts, asking us to consider how institutions generate habits, reasons and forms of rationality and conflicts among them. It thus situates akrasia as neither something for which the agent alone is responsible nor a momentary ‘epistemic sneeze’ (Rorty 1997) but encourages us to look to wider structures and contexts that shape the self. In this way, akrasia can be fruitfully linked to broader discussions about the social formation of attitudes, identities and (ir)rationality (see, for example, Comay del Junco 2018; Romaioli 2022; Szanto 2017). Second, while her own focus is on *individual* akrasia, her approach to the self contains valuable insights and materials for an account of *collective* akrasia, which is our goal.

For Rorty, making sense of akrasia requires a broadly ‘archeological’ account of the self. She (1987, p. 116) illustrates this with a striking metaphor which compares the self to a modern city, in which broad avenues that radiate from a central square containing

government buildings have been imposed over older, medieval ‘relatively autonomous neighborhoods, linked by small lanes that change their names half way across their paths, each with its distinctive internal organization’. What Rorty calls ‘standard theories of rational agency’ (by which she means something like Davidson’s) see only the modern, centralized vision, but attending to both levels reveals the self as ‘a loose configuration of habits, habits of thought and perception and motivation and action, acquired at different stages, in the service of different ends’ (Rorty 1987 p. 130).¹ These various habits are not pathological or alien, but rather are ‘standard operating procedures’ (Rorty 1980, p. 211), part of what make ‘ordinary rational action possible’ (Rorty 1987, p. 119).

On this view, akrasia results when an agent faces a conflict between those habits and thoughts that led them to identify a course of action as preferred and those habits and thoughts that are required to actualize that course of action (see Rorty 1980, p. 126). Faced with such a conflict, the agent ‘turns himself into a lower gear and follows the easier course, the course that is assured by relatively automatic psychological habits’ (1980, p. 208. See also Rorty 1987, p. 123). Rorty (1980, pp. 207-210; 1987, pp. 123-124) distinguishes three broad ways in which this can happen, which are neither mutually exclusive or exhaustive: 1. The akratic alternative dominates attention in some way, either due to its particular salience or attraction, or due to the relative lack of salience of the preferred alternative. 2. The akratic alternative might constitute ‘the familiar, the habitual, the easy course’, thus providing a ‘ready-made action solution’ (Rorty 1987, p.124). Such a course of action seems more attractive because it is made up of habits and routines that do not require extra motivation and, as habits, require extra motivation to deviate from. 3. Social streaming, which is grounded in our necessary psychological capacities for empathy and sympathy, can pull towards akratic alternatives. Habits and potential conflicts among them are also shaped by economic, social and political structures at several levels, from social expectations around drinking or smoking to larger social institutions and economic systems that ‘encourage and foster the very actions that they also condemn’ (Rorty 1997, p. 652).

Rorty’s account raises several potential objections, the responses to which help make clearer the stakes of her account: First, critics might worry that the archaeological account simply dissolves the agent into a set of variously competing habits and processes in which there is no longer any coherent self to speak of. For Rorty, however, this is why both visions of the city are necessary. An agent that is capable of akrasia must take ‘the unification of

¹ Readers familiar with psychoanalysis and similar approaches will no doubt find this metaphor absurdly simplistic. But Rorty should be read here as illustrating the limits of a more narrow and naïve view of agency, not as proposing a complete model, and her insights are clearly in tune with and open to more sophisticated psychoanalytic insights (as is the concept of akrasia itself, see Burnyeat 1980, p. 80).

his traits, his thoughts and his actions as a central project', must 'reflexively underwrite his integrative processes' and 'declare his various friendly neighborhood habits to be one city, the *I*' (1987, p. 131). This, she suggests, need not be true of all people, indeed, 'akrasia is among the diseases only the strong can suffer' (Rorty 1980, p. 176).

A second objection might ask in what sense akratic action is voluntary on Rorty's account. This might point both to her frequent recourse to the language of automaticity, gears, and operating procedures at the level of the individual and her focus on socially formed habits over which the individual has little control. Rorty's response to this rests on two connected claims: First, habitual action can be distinguished from compulsive, coerced or obsessive action such that the agent could have acted otherwise; and second, habits (whether socially shaped or not) form part of the agent's character, and the agent can be held responsible for them insofar as they are capable of shaping their own character (See Rorty, 1997, p. 656; Rorty 1980, p. 280). This leaves the line between akratic action and involuntary action somewhat hard to identify, 'nested in a system of conditionals and counterfactuals' (Rorty 1997 p. 645), and leaves open the temptation on the part of the agent to deny voluntariness by blaming their habits or social conditions. Nonetheless, this is a line she believes we can and do draw, both for ourselves and for others.

A third objection concerns the question of how far akasia ought to be seen as irrational or aberrant. The standard position here is that akasia is a form of practical irrationality. However, Rorty denies that the akratic alternative is necessarily irrational (1980, p. 200). Not only is it possible for reason to lie on both sides, but the preferred alternative might be preferred on grounds that the agent takes to be non-rational (for example, custom or tradition); conversely, the akratic alternative might involve careful exercise of prudential and instrumental reason (See Rorty 1997, pp. 650-651). Indeed, she resists the idea that akasia might be completely eliminated precisely because it results from *normal* psychological habits that 'provide the very stuff of rational thought' (Rorty 1987, p. 124). At the same time, however, she (1987, p. 129) insists that it is central to the experience of akasia that the agent 'cannot himself choose that course under a description that justifies it' and that akasia cannot be generally endorsed or validated (2017, p. 181). Thus, even if we might 'cut the akrates some slack', their condition remains an undesirable one.

Questions of rationality and responsibility raise a further question: is akasia necessarily *wrong*? In Aristotle's account, akasia is paradigmatically a moral failing, and he rejects as sophistry any possibility of 'reverse akasia', in which people come to do the right thing against values that they themselves endorse (e.g. cases like that of Huck Finn, whose personal sympathy for an enslaved man overrides his otherwise racist beliefs (See Arplay and Schroder 1999; Radoilska 2012)). However, accounts such as Davidson's and Rorty's

seem to have no problem labelling them as akratic: What matters is the agent's own beliefs about their ends, not whether those ends are objectively good. Akratic conflicts might also be seen by the agent as largely amoral (a choice between getting my work done this morning or making a third cup of coffee).²

While we are happy to remain neutral on the question of whether reverse or amoral akrasia is deserving of the label, it is important for the argument we develop here that akrasia appears as a failure to the agent themselves (at least on reflection), and is deserving of condemnation and criticism by those who share the agent's professed values. This latter aspect is particularly salient in contexts in which norms of responsibility and accountability come into play (which may be at stake even in apparently nonmoral choices). These norms, we suggest, are particularly significant when it comes to collective akrasia, to which we now turn.

2. Collective akrasia

In its classical form, akrasia is a feature of individual character. However, Aristotle already hints at an analogy with collective groups in passing in the *Nicomachean Ethics*: 'the incontinent person [akrates] is like a city [polis] that votes for all the right decrees and has excellent laws, but does not apply them' (Aristotle 1999, p. 113). This is a metaphor, of course, but the strength of a metaphor is often that it works both ways, and Aristotle was hardly alone among the Greeks in comparing the structure of a political community to that of the individual psyche (see e.g. Shields 2007). Might we then similarly say that the city that votes for the right laws but does not apply them is *also* an *akrates*?

The idea that *akrasia* might be ascribed to collective agents has been explored and defended by Philip Pettit. Pettit (2003, p. 78) imagines a group of people that 'establish[es] or grow[s] into a common purpose or purposes, on the basis of various levels of common belief'. Such a group, when pursuing those purposes, will face a variety of issues that it will need to resolve. This group first forms its decisions about how to address these issues through a series of majority votes. This method, however, readily permits (and even makes likely) 'the formation of judgements and intentions that fail to cohere with one another as a whole' (Pettit 2003, p. 73). This likelihood rests on the possibility (and indeed prevalence) of discursive dilemmas: Given the different choices available at different times, the aggregate

² Indeed, Rorty (1980, p. 195) goes so far as to suggest that the akratic alternative can be recognized by the akrites as the morally right one, imagining a Mafioso who fails to carry out a murder and reflects, 'despite my better judgement, and against my intention, morality has had its way with me'.

of votes may generate inconsistencies even if each individual member votes in an internally consistent manner.

A group that stopped at this point, however, would not be deserving of the label *akratic*, because it would not, according to Pettit, be an agent at all (2003, p. 75). However, groups need not stop there; they can instead ‘balk [...] in the event that the views thereby espoused—whether at the same or at different times—should prove not to cohere with one another, or not to cohere with the actions that it takes’ (2003, 78). Such a group would be sensitive to the demands of coherence and would ‘strive to endorse only views that can be integrated with one another into a single rational vision of how things are and of how it is desirable that they should be’ (2003, p. 79). This group would possess something analogous to Davidson’s principle of continence, or Rorty’s capacity for reflexive underwriting. It would be no less prone to generating inconsistencies, but it would possess the capacity and desire to correct them; if it nonetheless failed to do so, it would deserve the label *akratic*. Such groups are, in Pettit’s view, not particularly unusual, and include ‘public bodies or business corporations or private associations or [...] a few collaborators in some enterprise’ (Pettit 2003, p. 80).

The great value of Pettit’s account is that it vindicates the possibility of collective *akrasia* and draws an explicit analogy with individual *akrasia*. However, in doing so, his account is consciously reductive. His examples focus on small groups, and on the possibility and persistence of discursive dilemmas across even those small groups. While *akrasia* is manifested in incoherence among beliefs endorsed by the collective, this is ultimately reducible to the choices of individuals who refuse ‘to hear the call of the group as a whole and act [...] like encapsulated centers of voting who are responsive only to their own modular prompts’ (Pettit 2003, p. 84). This refusal might be grounded in any number of motives, either selfish or virtuous, and is only irrational for the individual to the extent that it matters to them that ‘the group should retain an uncontroversial claim to unity and agency in the domain in question’ (Pettit 2003, pp. 84-85). It is precisely in this respect that collective *akrasia* is analogous to individual *akrasia*, since these intransigent individuals are comparable to the various ‘voices that make a serious claim on the person’ (2003, p. 95).

Pettit’s treatment suggests a picture in which *akrasia* is manifested as a set of inconsistent decisions. At the group level, he presents a small journal editorial board making three different decisions at different times: In January, they vote to freeze subscription fees. In August, they send papers for review and vote to be bound by the recommendations of reviewers as to whether to publish. In December, they are faced with the choice of whether, in principle, to accept submission of papers containing complex theoretical apparatus that

is expensive to produce. The earlier decisions would seem to count against doing so (since it might result in being bound by reviewer recommendation to increase costs), but given the distribution of preferences among the members, it is conceivable that the collective might vote to do so without any one of them having voted *for all three* choices. Such a group would be practically irrational, and then would be faced with the choice of fully recognizing all members' preferences (and remaining irrational), or bringing their decisions in line with what reason demands.

Pettit captures something important about what collective akrasia might involve. However, it is striking how different this seems to be from paradigm cases of individual akrasia. These involve violations of beliefs and commitments that are deemed to be a significant part of the agent's character, most commonly ethical or moral commitments. They involve a conflict between a course of action taken and beliefs regarding the appropriate course of action to take. In contrast, Pettit's example involves an inconsistent set of decisions, taken in light of a set of general purposes, but where the conflict appears to be among the decisions, rather than between the decisions and the purposes.

We can see this difference at work in Pettit's own example of akrasia at the individual level: He imagines a man deciding whether to buy a Volvo, and composed of three selves: the 'economic self' who votes for buying a car but not an expensive Volvo; an 'ecological self' who votes against buying a car but prefers an ecological Volvo if there is to be any car at all; and a 'status-oriented self' who recommends the Volvo wholeheartedly. A voting procedure that asks (1) whether it is good to have a car, (2) whether Volvo is the best, and (3) whether to buy a Volvo would generate majority agreement on (1) and (2) but vote against (3): 'We might imagine the person who operates under the influence of such voices coming to the view that he or she should buy a Volvo but proving akratic when it comes to phoning the dealer' (Pettit 2003, p. 92). This case might be akratic according to something like Davidson's account, since the judgements in favor of buying a car and the judgement that the Volvo was best ought to lead to an all-things-considered judgement in favor of buying a Volvo. However, on Rorty's account, we would need more information: which of these 'selves' does the agent reflexively underwrite as providing the relevant reasons in this situation? What ends does the agent want to be guided by, and how have they entered into their reasoning? For someone who underwrites their ecological self (or the economic self), the failure to pick up the phone might be seen as *enkratic*, since it involves successfully overcoming status-oriented habits. *Experiencing* the decision not to pick up the phone as akratic would require that the agent underwrote the status-oriented self (at least as an equal to the other two selves). This is perfectly possible on Rorty's account – someone with

frugal habits might, on reflection, decide that there is nothing wrong with pursuing status but still struggle to shrug off their habits.³

This brings attention to a striking issue: while Pettit notes that the purposes are a feature of the formation of the group, his examples of akrasia do not refer to those purposes. Let us paint a somewhat different picture, sticking with the example of a journal editorial board: Imagine the journal has a fairly specific set of purposes: To promote research in an undeveloped area; to promote styles of writing that are not generally encouraged in academic journals; to provide space for articles in a language other than English. Suppose, at the same time, that they adopt much of the architecture and processes of more established journals; to attract authors they ensure that they are indexed in certain databases and do what they can to maximize their rankings within those databases. They look back after 5 years and discover they have become a rather ‘successful’ journal based on various metrics and rankings. But, they have in fact overwhelmingly published papers in a conventional academic style and in the English language. This is a source of collective regret.

How might we explain this happening? The purposes were not revised, no one changed their mind; there’s no reason to believe they were not sincerely committed to these purposes from the beginning. But, on reflection, they realize that they too often did things on ‘autopilot’ and kept returning to ‘business as usual’. They fell into simple routines regarding styles of reviewing, editing and feedback. They behaved in ways that were expected of them as a journal and allowed themselves to be guided by certain incentives. These behaviors were not alien to them – as academics they were very *familiar* behaviours, and ones that in other contexts they were happy to endorse (or at least play along with). They may have had moments of doubt along the way, expressed as individuals or even discussed formally in meetings. But they slipped easily into such routines when ‘push came to shove’.

This case provides something closer to an analogy with Rorty’s account of akrasia. The group can be understood as shifting into a lower gear, allowing established routines to dominate, or failing to carry their habits along with their preferred commitments. One upshot of this account is that, unlike in Pettit’s account, we needn’t reduce the explanation of akrasia to the intransigence of individuals or model the different competing demands on the agent in terms of specific individuals (or different ‘selves’). The different competing

³ This also draws out a significant difference between the Davidson and Rorty approaches – the preferred alternative might not be an ‘all-things-considered’ judgement *if* that involves taking into account aspects of a person’s character they would rather not act on or would not reflexively endorse in that domain.

routines, systems and habits might be attributable to specific members of the collective, but they might exist and operate across the entire collective, or groups within it.

3. Governmental akrasia and climate inaction

Assuming that something like what we describe in our editorial board example is a) possible and b) appropriately described as collective akrasia, we now want to suggest that this might be appropriately applied to governments, and that it might helpfully illuminate the specific case of inaction on climate change.

First, can governments be considered akratic agents in the sense developed in the previous section? To begin, note that our claim is not, as the quotation from Aristotle above implies, that the entire political community (or society) can be described as such. Rather, we focus on a narrower group of people, loosely those who govern and who possess executive power. While precisely who compose the ‘government’ will vary across different states and societies, we suggest it is a relatively clearly defined and bounded group of people. While there may be borderline cases, it is relatively easy to identify in ordinary parlance who is ‘in government’ and who is not.

Once identified, we suggest, such groups meet Pettit’s criteria for a collectively akratic agent. They are groups of people that come together with some shared purposes, face choices in the course of pursuing those purposes, and make decisions and form judgements about those choices in light of various beliefs. Our everyday language sees nothing peculiar in this. Governments express and form their purposes as a combination of beliefs about the appropriate ends of government in general (protecting citizens, securing social justice, etc.) and the specific ideological ends of a given party, faction or project (reforming capitalism, ending wokeness). These might be those expressed in a manifesto or party program (in the case of a majority government) or in a coalition agreement, or they might be pledges or commitments made later (the current British government gives a taste of the linguistic variety of this, having made six pre-election ‘pledges’, shifting five months later into five ‘missions’, to be judged according to six ‘milestones’ (Belger 2024)). Such government beliefs are sometimes actively distinguished from those of its individual members – “Well, look, that’s not the view of the government” – and doing so is sometimes an important political move. Moreover, governments as collectives possess the capacity to reflect on and revise these various beliefs, intentions and actions in a way that can bring them into coherence. While the processes by which governments make decisions are often opaque, they do not (or needn’t) involve only a sequence of majority votes, but draw on

notions of collective discussion (both formal and informal) and connected ideas of collective responsibility.⁴

If this is true, then governments are capable of *akrasia* in Pettit's sense – i.e. of forming contradictory decisions about courses of action which they *could* resolve through reflection but do not in fact resolve. Are they also capable of the kind of Rortyan *akrasia* that we ascribed to our hypothetical editorial board – one grounded in routine and the failure carry their habits along with their commitments?

We think so, and to motivate this, we will turn to an example related to our specific case of climate/emissions policy. When announcing and defending three major new oil pipeline projects, Canadian Prime Minister Justin Trudeau insisted 'no country would find 173 billion barrels of oil in the ground and just leave them there. The resource will be developed. Our job is to ensure this is done responsibly, safely and sustainably' (Maclean's 2017). This example requires some nuancing: Let us assume that this was an expression of the government's position. Let us also assume that the references to 'responsibility' and 'sustainability' reflect sincere values endorsed by the government and their invocation in this context indicates some recognition of a tension; let us go further, and assume that the government sees these values as part of an overall environmental commitment and that they believe this commitment requires the reduction of carbon emissions, which could certainly be aided by leaving oil in the ground. What seems to be at stake, then, is a conflict between those commitments and some idea of what it is normal and acceptable for a 'country' to do upon discovering significant oil deposits.

This example is idealized and imperfect: Perhaps Trudeau's government does not have environmental purposes at all; perhaps they figure quite low down on a ranking of purposes that means they genuinely do not determine the government's preferred alternative in this case; perhaps the government sincerely values "doing what a country would do" over its other ideological commitments, and so is acting *enkratically*. However, it is striking that the reasons advanced for the action are essentially habitual and do not refer to named values. Just as in our hypothetical editorial board, these are not reasons that are *alien* to the government – quite the opposite, they are intensely familiar to them. Nonetheless, it does not seem implausible to imagine that, on reflection, this is a decision that the government will come to regret, precisely because it was not compatible with purposes that were more deeply held and reflexively endorsed.

⁴ Of course, one could imagine a government that merely made decisions based on a series of majority votes at each cabinet meeting; such a government's agency would indeed be as non-existent as the plausibility of the government itself.

If we accept this as a description of what happened, we might explain *how* it happened by identifying the various ways in which the assumptions of ‘what a government does’ were able to appear as in conflict with and override the explicitly identified values. One obvious culprit would be the widespread assumption that a primary role of governments is to provide and stimulate economic growth. Growth, measured in terms of GDP increase, came, in the second half of the twentieth century, to be seen as almost identical with (or at least a sufficient proxy for) social progress and development, and in the process became seen as both a necessary means for governments to pursue other ends, and an end in itself (Barry 2020; Schmelzer 2018). Economic growth thus became ideological in the sense that it began to appear as natural, normal and indisputable. Governments no longer needed to explicitly declare their commitment to growth (although they sometimes do) – growth’s priority was simply taken for granted. Such commitments might thus be seen as analogous to the way that our hypothetical editorial board readily endorsed database rankings and allowed them to guide and shape their work: A quantitative proxy measure for what counts as good, which in certain cases can conflict with purposes and thus badly misjudging success.

A further culprit might be found in what Simon Caney (2019) calls the ‘political organisation of attention’. This draws on Eviatar Zerubavel’s (2015) sociological account of the ‘social organisation of attention’, which extends psychological and physiological observations about patterns of perception into questions of social relevance and irrelevance. What appears to a given person or group as relevant is a product of how ‘we are *socialized* into culturally, subculturally (ideologically, professionally), and historically specific norms, conventions and *traditions* of attending that actually determine what we come to regard as attention-worthy and what we effectively ignore’ (Zerubavel 2015, p. 10). Different attentional communities are socialized through different attentional norms to focus on different elements of the social and phenomenal world; moreover, members of those groups do not attend as individuals, but also as collectives, which presuppose a *shared sense of relevance* and therefore implicitly also a shared notion of irrelevance.

Applied to governments, we might look for the specific patterns of salience generated both by the professional norms of politics – common assumptions and clichés of what *really* matters and what does not (‘It’s the economy, stupid’). The pioneering climate scientist James Hansen (2009, p. 69) recalls how frequently his attempts to change government approaches were confronted by various clichés that served to put off and stymie action: ‘The principal reasons given were these: (1) *Do not let the perfect be the enemy of the good* [...]; (2) *the train has left the station*—it would be counterproductive to take a different approach; and (3) *we will improve the system later.*’ Hansen, perhaps correctly in his case, sees these clichés as cynically and dishonestly deployed to mask a deeper denialism, but

it is easy to see how they might appear not as deliberate strategies, but as normal, habitual modes of thinking that shape patterns of attention and relevance. We might also look, as Caney does, to the way in which wider political structures incentivize some forms of attention and not others, notably through inculcating forms of short-termism that easily displace questions of climate. Of course, to link these to akrasia, it cannot be that the desired alternative was *never* given attention or showed up as significant; rather, ‘when push came to shove’, it too easily faded from view into a background of irrelevance.

As with our editorial board example, these pressures come both from ‘outside’, in the sense that they are imposed by various kinds of social and institutional expectations, and from ‘within’, insofar as the members of the institution tacitly or explicitly endorse some of these expectations.

4. Responding to objections

A first possible objection to what we propose here might follow from the examples with which we ended the previous: we already have a perfectly good set of concepts for talking about why governments do not take sufficient action on climate. These have already been hinted at: growth ideology, capitalist economic logic, short-termism in our political institutions and patterns of thinking, the psychology of denial. In response, we want to stress that akrasia is not intended to compete with these other explanations, but rather to complement them. As we stressed in our discussion of Rorty, adequately situating akrasia within social and political contexts opens dialogue with other approaches, rather than displacing them.

At the same time, akrasia offers something distinctive, insofar as it picks out a distinct kind of wrongdoing or defective form of action (see Comay del Junco 2018). Criticising someone for their akratic character is different from criticizing them as ignorant, vicious or powerless, and the same goes for political institutions like governments. That does, we suggest, capture something about the character of *some* governments. Moreover, it is something worthy of condemnation, at least insofar as we believe that governments have some kinds of duties of accountability to their citizens when it comes to their beliefs and commitments. As we discussed above, even if akrasia is not the moral failing that Aristotle took it to be, it is something that the agent cannot consistently endorse from their own perspective. The context of politics, however, necessarily introduces a second-person perspective from which it is worthy of condemnation. I might not care about my friend’s or colleague’s akrasia *until* it prevents them keeping commitments that affect me and that I care about; governments are already in that situation.

This, however, might raise deeper objections that suggest we have misunderstood something important about politics. Broadly, there are two forms this might take. The first,

more ‘pessimistic,’ view might be to suggest that in fact our account gives far more credit to government action (and intention) than it deserves. One version of this might suggest that government action is in fact largely unfree, determined by circumstances outside of its control. Governments are perhaps weak and powerless in the face of various vested interests; their space for action is in fact paltry.⁵ Alternatively, we might suggest that various statements discussed above ought not to be read as sincere commitments, but as propaganda, political campaigning, or even outright dishonesty. Critics might also challenge our claim that the ‘government’ is a clearly defined group, pointing to examples such as Britain’s ‘Conservative government’ of 2019-2024, which had 3 Prime Ministers and a rate of resignation and demotion that meant that cabinet ministers only remained in post for an average of 8 months (Difford 2024). They might, finally, suggest that governments do not possess genuine or sufficient capacities for collective decision-making and reflection; real governments are in fact a chaotic combination of horse-trading, grandstanding and firefighting, rarely engaged in genuine reflection.

A more ‘optimistic’ version of the same criticism might point towards the nature of democratic politics. Political decision-making cannot be modelled according to the behaviour of individual agents (or even Pettit’s integrated groups), because its central purpose (in a democratic society at least) is to reflect, represent, balance or reconcile the competing interests and perspectives of society. Apparent contradictions and inconsistencies are thus attributable not to failures of agency, but to the entirely normal procedures of democratic government. Moreover, these inconsistencies, while frustrating for specific members of society, are *positive successes*, insofar as they manifest politics’ (or at least democratic politics’) central purpose of reconciling competing interests. To this, it might be added that voters and the general public are fully aware that a government cannot do everything it promises. On this reading, then, the government is either not truly a coherent subject, since its action is driven by a need to reflect and reconcile conflicting desires that lie outside it, or its conflicted status is in some sense constitutive of its agency, a feature, not a bug, and therefore any ascription of akrasia as failure is missing the point.

In response to these objections, let us first acknowledge that in many cases the ‘pessimistic’ reading will be the correct one – it is quite possible that some governments will have their status as subject so compromised as to make any ascription of akrasia meaningless; and some governments might just lie. Likewise, some forms of inaction might be understood, as the ‘optimistic’ view has it, as either the product of conscious and

⁵ Or, perhaps, the various habitual tendencies we point to in the previous section should not be located within the government, but permanent structures of the state – the civil service, independent central banks, constitutional courts, etc. Thus, they appear as external constraints on agency, rather than as something within the agency of the subject.

deliberate compromise, or as precisely *flowing from* a sincere commitment to democratic representation ('we simply let the people decide'). (Note, though, that such claims might also be posthoc rationalizations for various akratic slippages, similar to those Rorty points to at the individual level.)

However, it seems doubtful that these exhaust all cases. While these beliefs are in some sense reflective of the beliefs of the people that the government seeks to represent, they are not a *mere* reflection or algorithmic aggregation and balancing. Governments, as political actors themselves, both *select among* the different competing opinions of society to decide which are worthy of representation and which are not (and which might be 'compromised with'), and, as much democratic theory has come to emphasize, partially *constitute* those opinions through their own political communications and forms of address. Moreover, voters, activists, campaigners and other politicians *have* to take these at face value in some sense, and to address governments *as if* they were agents who can be judged on the consistency of these commitments and their record of carrying them through.

Responding to these objections thus brings into clearer light one of the contributions we think employing the language of akrasia can make. These postures require taking the government *as if* it can act as a consistent agent in the way that, on the individual level, we approach the *akrates*. There will be occasions, clearly, where this approach is inappropriate, when it is better to point to either the structural factors that make government action impossible, or where professed claims are mere dishonest 'greenwashing'. But to reduce all discussion to such occasions would be to impoverish the language of politics, and undermine important capacities to hold governments to account. Indeed, even if it turns out governments are *not* capable of making an honest judgement (and thus strictly speaking are not akratic), there may be strategic value to approaching them as such. For example, Deborah Javeline (2003) has shown how identifying blameworthy actors helps motivate people to express grievances and engage in collective action. Returning to Rorty, we can think of governments as composed of both the centralized functions in the modern city square and the various medieval communities that lie below it. We need to attend to the different medieval neighborhoods to see how they both enable and stymie the central functions. But we sometimes need to be able to protest in the central square, and address the agent as a whole.

Conclusion

As these last comments suggest, we think that bringing the language of akrasia into political contexts can play a valuable role in holding governments to account. We think, moreover, that the failures of apparently sympathetic governments to act on climate

change provides a useful case for thinking through these issues, precisely because they *appear* to be cases where governments act against their stated values and commitments. In this way, we believe that deploying the notion of akrasia expands the vocabulary available to those who wish to criticize those governments. In particular, it introduces a wrong that is not dependent on causing direct harm to existing or future generations, or one rooted in questions of environmental or generational justice. Important though these issues are, they introduce moral and legal complexities that often make it harder to hold governments directly to account; a government that acts akratically is in the wrong whether or not someone is harmed.

Akrasia also, however, opens broader reflection on questions of government agency and accountability – even if it turns out that akrasia is the wrong diagnosis in this case (even *always* the wrong diagnosis), it might be useful to consider why. If, for example, we conclude that our politics is structured so that governments do not even meet the requirements of collective agency, it might be worth confronting that fact seriously and soberly, and considering how to adapt either our language or, preferably, our political and social structures. This indicates the final contribution that the concept of akrasia might make. Returning to Aristotle’s original intent, presenting akrasia as a *diagnosis* draws our attention to the various possible places for *reform*, both within governments and outside them, and by citizens and politicians alike.

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